

adjusted to expose 60-d-old seedlings to 12-14°C air temperature for about 30 d. They were scored for leaf discoloration using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The F₂ segregation had

165 tolerant (score 3) plants, 380 moderately tolerant (score 5), and 185 susceptible (score 7-9) plants, a perfect 1:2:1 with a nonsignificant χ^2 , that indicated a monogenic inheritance for

leaf discoloration with incomplete dominance for green leaf color. The study is preliminary and no confirmation of the genetic ratio was done with F₃ progenies of backcross generations. □

Cold-tolerant rice variety MDU2

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Cold damage is a serious constraint to rice yields in the high-altitude zone of Tamil Nadu, where in winter, minimum temperature is 14.5 to 16.0°C. MDU2, a promising cold-tolerant rice variety, was approved by the Tamil Nadu State Varietal Release Committee in Jan 1984 for cultivation in the Cumbum Valley of Madurai district. MDU2 is a hybrid cross of C0-25 and IR8.

In station trials, MDU2 yielded 28%

Average yield^a of MDU2, Madurai, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		
	Research station trial (1)	Multilocation trials (23) ^b	Rice Coordinated Yield trials (8)
MDU2	3.7	6.1	4.4
IR20	2.9	5.5	3.7
Increase over IR20 (%)	28	11	19

^a Numbers in parentheses indicate sites from which yields were averaged. ^b Trials were conducted at the hot spot area.

more than IR20, and in 23 yield evaluation trials on farmer fields it yielded 11% more. In the rice coordinated yield trials, MDU2 yielded an average 19% more than IR20 (see table).

Spikelet sterility was 23% for MDU2 versus 45% for IR20. MDU2 is a medium-duration (130-135 d), semidwarf variety

with medium tillering ability and good panicle exertion. Grains are medium slender with white kernels, and grain type is acceptable to local consumers. It has some tolerance for leaf blight, gall midge, leafroller, and stem borer, and is recommended for cultivation in the second crop season (Oct-Feb) in the Cumbum Valley. □

Pest management and control DISEASES

Relative amount of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in an infected plant

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Scoring of rice varieties resistance to RSV has been based on percentage of infected seedlings. Using this method, it is

Reaction of extracts of Mawee and TNI infected with RSV at 30 d after inoculation. IRRI, 1984.

Relative amounts of RSV in infected rice plants on different days after inoculation, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to RSV ^a	Absorbance at 405 nm of extracts in ELISA		
		30 DAI ^b	45 DAI ^b	60 DAI ^c
Ptb 21	I	0.38 bc	0.48	0.25 ns
Murungakayan	R	0.28 c	0.64	0.32
Mawee	R	0.88 a	1.08	0.75
Balaratawee	R	0.83 a	0.93	0.56
Hathili	R	0.80 a	1.43	0.40
IR22	I	0.84 a	0.91	0.69
IR50	R	0.70 ab	0.87	0.21
TN1	S	0.78 ab	0.91	0.55
Average		0.69	0.90	0.47

^a Results of mass screening were based on 0-30% infection = R, 31-60% infection = I, 61-100% infection = S. DAI= days after inoculation. In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different. ns: not significant. ^b Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:200 dilution. ^c Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:160 dilution.

not clear whether the resistant varieties are resistant to RSV infection or to virus multiplication. Therefore, we determined the resistance of eight selected varieties and the relative amount of the virus in each variety by mass screening and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Seven-d-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated at five brown plant-

hoppers/seedling and then grown in the greenhouse. One month later, three infected seedlings were selected from each variety and transplanted singly in clay pots. At 30, 45, and 60 d after inoculation, extracts of the whole plant, except the root, were tested by ELISA. γ -globulin was coated with 2.5 μ g/ml and γ -globulin/alkaline phosphate conjugate was diluted 300 times. The relative